

Metal Complexes of Sulphathiazole Salicylaldimine (SUTSA)

R. R. GUPTA and R. KAUSHAL*

Department of Chemistry, Holkar Science College, Indore (M.P.)

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The complexes of Sulphathiazole salicylaldimine (SUTSA) with copper, manganese, iron and cobalt when studied by conductometric titrations and Job's method of continuous variation showed 2:1 complexation. The complexes are highly coloured. Their stability constants ($\log k$) and the free energy of formation (ΔF) are evaluated.

SULPHONAMIDES are drugs of established therapeutic value. Butler and Ingle¹ have condensed sulphonamides with salicylaldehyde and have isolated various sulphonamide salicylaldimines. Takeo Tsukamoto prepared sulphonamide bromo salicylaldimines^{2,3} and found them to be effective against *mycobacterium tuberculosis*.

The complexes of Schiff base of sulphanilamide have been studied, (1) with nickel, copper and sodium by Maria Macrovi⁴ *et al* and (2) with copper, nickel, cobalt and manganese by Mukherjea and Ray⁵. They found 2:1 complexation.

Not much work seem to have been done on metal complexes of sulphonamide salicylaldimines. There-

fore considering the importance of bromosalicylaldimines, we have undertaken a detailed investigation of the complexes of sulphonamide salicylaldimines. Here in we describe the SUTSA complexes with some transition metals of therapeutic importance *viz*, copper, manganese, iron and cobalt.

Experimental

The materials used, were either of E.P. or of AnalaR grade:

Sulphathiazole Salicylaldimine (SUTSA) was prepared by shaking a molar solution of sulphathiazole (2.55 g.) in hot ethanol with molar quantity of sali-

Fig. 1.

*Retired Professor of Applied Chemistry (M.P.E.S.)

cyaldehyde (1.22 g), when yellow-orange crystals separated in about 15 min, which were filtered,

TABLE I—STABILITY CONSTANTS

Sl. No.	Complex	α	Stability constant (log K)	Dissociation constant	ΔF°
1.	Cu-SUTSA	0.1569	4.44	0.3639×10^{-4}	-2.63 K Cals per mole
2.	Mn-SUTSA	0.08943	4.96	0.1097×10^{-4}	-2.94 K Cals per mole
3.	Fe-SUTSA	0.1622	3.41	0.3925×10^{-4}	-2.02 K Cals per mole
4.	Co-SUTSA	0.3103	3.76	0.1744×10^{-4}	-2.26 K Cals per mole

washed and recrystallised from ethanol; yield 2.45 g, m.p. 228°-9° (lit. 229°).

Results and Discussion

Conductometric titrations were carried out with 20 ml of 0.01M SUTSA dissolved and diluted to 200 ml in 4% aqueous pyridine against 0.02M metal salt dissolved in the same solvent, using conductivity bridge (W.T.W. German) and dip type conductivity

All the conductivity measurements were done at 25°. After making the volume correction, the titration results are plotted in Fig. 1, which clearly indicates that SUTSA forms 2 : 1 complexes with copper, manganese, iron and cobalt.

Job's method of continuous variation⁶ was also applied to determine the metal ligand ratio using $1.25 \times 10^{-3}M$ solutions and conductivity as the index property. The results are depicted in Fig. 2, which confirm 2 : 1 complexation.

The stability constants were determined by extrapolation of these Job curves as suggested by Raghav-
rao⁷ using the expression

$$Ks = \frac{(1-\alpha)}{\alpha^2 c}$$

where α is degree of dissociation and c is concentration. The results are recorded in Table I.

Fig. 2

cell (cell constant 0.616). 4% aqueous pyridine was prepared in specially prepared conductivity water.

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